

1 **ChlamytinaTool: An Integrative Epigenomic Platform for Investigating**
2 **Stress Adaption in *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii***

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13 **Running title:** ChlamytinaTool: *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* epigenomic platform

14 **Abstract**

15 Algal species are frequently exposed to suboptimal environmental conditions that
16 impede their growth and development. Epigenetic mechanisms, such as histone
17 modifications, DNA methylation, and chromatin remodelling, has been identified as key
18 regulators in coordinating stress responses and adaptative process. However, the
19 interplay between epigenomic, transcriptomic, and proteomic layers remains poorly
20 understood. To overcome this limitation, we developed ChlamytinaTool, an integrative
21 platform that compiles epigenomic data from the algal model species *Chlamydomonas*
22 *reinhardtii*, including chromatin immunoprecipitation coupled to next generation
23 sequencing (ChIP-seq), whole genome bisulfite (WGBS), methylated DNA precipitation
24 (MeDIP-seq), and micrococcal nuclease digestion (MNase-seq). Using ChromHMM
25 software, we generated a new universal chromatin states model based on eleven
26 epigenetic marks: histone modifications (H3K4me3, H3K4me2, H3K9me3, H3K36me3,
27 H3K27me3 and H3K27ac), DNA methylation (5mC and 6mA), nucleosome positioning,
28 RNA polymerase II and PSR1 transcription factor. ChlamytinaTool enabled the
29 integration of epigenetic marks and chromatin states with transcriptomic and proteomic
30 data, offering new insights into regulatory mechanisms underlying stress adaptation. By
31 combining a previously generated proteomic dataset characterizing *C. reinhardtii*
32 response to combined heat and drought stress, we identified key molecular genes

33 activated under simultaneous stress conditions, uncovering adaptive responses and
34 potential trade-offs. To validate these *in silico* findings, we applied a ChIP protocol
35 coupled with MNase digestion and qPCR. Results revealed dynamic changes in the
36 H3K4me3 mark under combined heat and drought stress conditions, highlighting its role
37 in activating stress-responsive genes. This study emphasizes the relevance of
38 integrating epigenomic data into stress biology, providing novel insights into the
39 molecular mechanisms of environmental adaptation.

40 **Keywords:** epigenomics, chromatin states, microalgae, stress adaption, systems
41 biology.

42 Introduction

43 Climate change stands out as one of the greatest challenges currently facing the planet,
44 leading to a multifactorial combination of abiotic stresses (IPCC, 2023). This global
45 phenomenon is increasingly manifesting as a co-occurrence of heatwaves and droughts,
46 creating complex environmental pressures that significantly impact ecosystems and their
47 resilience (Exposito-Alonso, 2023; Teskey et al., 2015; Teuling, 2018). Moreover,
48 acclimation and evolution are processes requiring coordinated changes in many traits
49 according to selective environmental pressures (Roces et al., 2022). Within the broad
50 array of cellular strategies activated in response to stress, epigenetic regulation stands
51 out as a central mechanism modulating gene expression in a highly dynamic and
52 context-dependent manner (Mirouze and Paszkowski, 2011). Epigenetic mechanisms,
53 such as histone modifications, DNA methylation, and chromatin remodelling, play a
54 central role in regulating gene expression without altering the underlying DNA sequence.
55 It is known that epigenetic mechanisms play critical roles in stress response serving as
56 link between environmental cues and genomic function (Cavalli and Heard, 2019;
57 Gallusci et al., 2017). These processes act as molecular switches that enable rapid and
58 reversible responses, thereby facilitating the reprogramming of transcriptomic,
59 proteomic, and metabolic networks during stress adaptation. A particularly relevant
60 concept emerging from integrative epigenomics is that of chromatin states, which result
61 from specific combinations of epigenetic marks and reflect distinct functional
62 configurations of the genome, such as active transcription, repression, or poised
63 regulatory regions (Stricker et al., 2017). Studying these chromatin states allows us to
64 interpret the genome in terms of its regulatory potential, rather than its static sequence
65 (Probst and Mittelsten Scheid, 2015). However, the knowledge about how cell
66 orchestrates a coordinated stress response between the epigenome, the transcriptome,

67 and the proteome is far to be understood (Kumar and Rani, 2023; Mirouze and
68 Paszkowski, 2011).

69 Algae represent a very large and diverse polyphyletic group of photosynthetic
70 eukaryotes. They thrive in all possible ecological niches on Earth, making them a rich
71 reservoir of untapped functional traits for environmental adaptation (Blaby-Haas and
72 Merchant, 2019). Among algae, the unicellular alga *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*
73 (hereafter referred as *Chlamydomonas*) stands out as model organism (Merchant et al.,
74 2007; Salomé and Merchant, 2019). Algae are increasingly exposed to fluctuating
75 environmental conditions, requiring profound physiological and molecular adaptations.
76 Experimental studies simulating abiotic stresses such as heat, cold, UV, and drought
77 have revealed that these adaptative responses are orchestrated through major
78 transcriptomic, proteomic, and epigenomic reprogramming (Carbó et al., 2025; Colina et
79 al., 2020b, 2020a; Valledor et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2022). In algae, epigenetic
80 regulation has been increasingly recognized as a key integrative layer that connects
81 environmental perception to functional responses (Bacova et al., 2020; Carbó et al.,
82 2025; Steadman, 2023). Despite its pivotal role, the precise mechanism by which
83 epigenetic regulation, and specifically chromatin organization, contributes to stress
84 adaption remain poorly understood (Carballo et al., 2025). This knowledge gap highlights
85 the need for integrative approaches that combine epigenomic data with other omic layers
86 to fully elucidate the molecular basis of environmental adaptation.

87 Epigenetic analyses were classically analysed as an independent layer providing
88 analyses focused on correlation rather on causality. However, nowadays we have
89 powerful tools for integrating regulatory layers at genome level with transcriptomics and
90 proteomics. This approach provides invaluable functional information for understanding
91 epigenetic regulation as a core mechanism within cell regulation allowing answering
92 fundamental questions such as how is epigenome reacting to environmental
93 fluctuations? Is epigenome coordinating cell responses? or simpler, could my gene of
94 interest be epigenetically regulated? Despite *Chlamydomonas* being a model organism,
95 with several high throughput epigenomic (~20 studies, based on NCBI), transcriptomic
96 (~60 studies, based on NCBI and EMBL-EBI Expression Atlas) and proteomic (~90
97 studies, from the EMBL-EBI Proteomics Identification Database) datasets, to our
98 knowledge, no integrative framework focusing on epigenetic regulation, or even a
99 centralized standardized data repository, is yet available. This situation limits current
100 epigenetic research in this species.

101 As a first necessary step for elucidating the epigenetic pathways underlying stress
102 responses in *Chlamydomonas*, we created ChlamytinaTool, a specialised resource
103 aimed to ease and consolidate epigenetic studies on this model organism.
104 ChlamytinaTool integrates histone modifications, DNA methylation, and nucleosome
105 positioning datasets, incorporating them into a novel chromatin state model to facilitate
106 deeper exploration of regulatory mechanisms. Building on this foundation, we combined
107 the epigenomic data from ChlamytinaTool with a proteomic dataset of the microalga in
108 response to combined heat and drought stress (Álvarez et al. 2025). This integrative
109 approach allowed a first step towards understanding the regulatory mechanisms
110 underlying stress response, setting the stage for a more comprehensive view of how
111 *Chlamydomonas* acclimates to increasingly complex environmental challenges. We
112 observed a selective epigenetic remodelling under stress, highlighting a strategically
113 reconfiguration of the H3K4me3 pattern, activating defense-related genes and
114 repressing anabolic functions. Out of these gene candidates, *N-TERMINAL*
115 *ACETYLTRANSFERASE (NAT1)*, *DEAD BOX ATP-DEPENDENT RNA HELICASE*
116 *(HEL12)*, *MITOCHONDRIAL F1F0 ATP SYNTHASE, BETA SUBUNIT (ATP12)*, and
117 *CHAPERONIN 60C (CPN60C)* were biologically validated combining Chromatin
118 Immunoprecipitation (ChIP) coupled with micrococcal nuclease (MNase) digestion and
119 qPCR quantification, proving the precision of the tool and the functional relevance of
120 these epigenetic mechanisms in the response to combined heat and drought stress.
121 Beyond this specific context, this platform proves valuable for investigating a wide range
122 of environmental scenarios, enabling a more precise and reliable exploration of
123 epigenetic mechanisms in *Chlamydomonas*, and offering deeper insights into the
124 regulatory processes that govern stress responses.

125 Results

126 ChlamytinaTool: implementation, chromatin states, and down-stream 127 analysis

128 The integration of eleven public epigenomic datasets allowed us to report the most
129 extensive compilation of diverse epigenetic marks available for *Chlamydomonas*,
130 encompassing distinct modifications: 5mC, 6mA, H3K4me3, H3K9me3, H3K4me2,
131 H3K36me3, H3K27me3, H3K27ac, nucleosome positioning, RNA polymerase II
132 occupancy, and the transcription factor PSR1 (**Figure 1A-B**). The resulting platform,
133 ChlamytinaTool, also includes a region-based enrichment analysis module, enabling
134 users to assess the overlap between proteins or transcripts and epigenetic marks or

135 chromatin states (CS) included in the tool. In addition, it offers extended functionality for
136 downstream analysis of proteins and transcripts, as well as an epigenome browser
137 designed for site-specific exploration of the epigenomic landscape.

138 A universal CS map annotation was generated using the eleven previously described
139 epigenetic marks, employing ChromHMM software (**Figure 1C**). To determine the
140 optimal number of states, we evaluated models from 2 to 40 CS. For each state number,
141 eleven models with different initializations were tested (one based on information criteria
142 and ten with random seeds). Although the 40-state model demonstrated the best
143 mathematical fit, its complexity posed challenges for biological interpretation. Therefore,
144 a 23-state model was selected as the optimal trade-off between model performance and
145 interpretability. To ensure robustness, up to 500 models were trained for the 23-state
146 configuration and compared against the eleven models of the 40-state configuration to
147 identify the best-performing model. The final CS were grouped into five functional
148 categories based on the presence and de combination of specific epigenetic marks.
149 Specifically, six states were classified as active, characterized by enrichment in
150 activation-associated marks; three as repressive, defined by the presence of repressive
151 marks; and twelve as bivalent, containing both active and repressive features.
152 Additionally, two states were designated as ambiguous low-signal and no detectable
153 signal (quiescent). To facilitate biological interpretation, CS were annotated based on
154 their distribution across various genomic features, including: 5' untranslated regions
155 (5'UTR), 3'UTR TSS + 2 kb (promoter region), transcription start sites (TSS),
156 transcription end site (TES), repetitions and low complexity regions (Reps LC), intron,
157 exon, intergenic, genes, and CpG islands.

158 Epigenetic regulation under combined heat and drought stress

159 Out of the 1444 proteins previously semi-quantified in the combined heat and drought
160 stress experiment (Álvarez et al. 2025) (**Table S1**), ChlamytinaTool revealed 743 proteins
161 differentially accumulated in at least one treatment (p -value ≤ 0.05). A total of 296
162 proteins were differentially accumulated between control and stress at different time
163 points: 19 at 5 h, 91 at 72 h, and 87 at 120 h. The highest number (219) appeared at 24
164 h, with 154 being exclusive to this time (**Figure 2A**). To further explore the functional
165 roles of the exclusive proteins at 24 h, we performed a functional enrichment analysis
166 based on MapMan categories (**Figure 2B**). Proteins that were upregulated under stress
167 at 24 h were predominantly enriched in cellular respiration, carbohydrate metabolism,
168 redox homeostasis, and photosynthesis, suggesting metabolic reprogramming to
169 maintain energy and redox balance. Downregulated proteins were linked to biosynthesis,

170 secondary metabolism, and transport-related processes, indicating possible energy-
171 saving adaptations. Once their roles in key functional processes were identified, we
172 explored whether the accumulation of these proteins could be linked to epigenetic
173 regulatory mechanisms.

174 Using the epigenetic enrichments module of ChlamytinaTool an enrichment analysis in
175 epigenetic marks was conducted to investigate the role of this layer over the regulation
176 of proteome remodelling under combined heat and drought stress conditions (**Figure**
177 **2C**). When the whole proteome was used as the background (universe background),
178 significant enrichment was revealed for the histone modifications H3K36me3, H3K27ac,
179 and H3K4me3 (associated with active chromatin) as well as H3K27me3 and H3K9me3
180 (associated with repressive chromatin). Additionally, enrichment was observed in DNA
181 methylation at adenine (6mA), RNA polymerase II, and the transcription factor PSR1, all
182 of which are linked to active marks. When only the differentially expressed proteins were
183 used as the background (differential background), a distinct temporal enrichment pattern
184 emerged: at 24 hours, enrichment was prominent for the active marks H3K4me3 and
185 RNA polymerase II. At 5 hours, enrichment was observed for the repressive mark
186 H3K27me3, while PSR1 was enriched at 5, 72, and 120 hours.

187 Chromatin states offer a more integrative and functional perspective of gene regulation,
188 as they combine multiple epigenetic marks and regulatory features, rather than focusing
189 on isolated signals. To further investigate epigenetic regulation, CS generated in
190 ChlamytinaTool were also used as region data base to perform enrichments (**Figure 2D**).
191 Considering the universe background, the stress response was primarily associated with
192 active (CS1, CS5, and CS6) and bivalent (CS7, CS12, CS13, CS14, and CS16) CS. With
193 the differential background, the stress response exhibited a time-dependent regulatory
194 pattern: early stress (5 h), dominated by CS12 (bivalent), which also influenced the 24-
195 hour response; mid stress (24 h), involved CS13 (bivalent) and CS6 (active); and late
196 stress (72 and 120 h), governed by CS1 and CS3 (both active).

197 H3K4me3 links to gene expression in differentially expressed proteins 198 under heat and drought stress

199 We selected 24-hour time point for an additional comparative PTM enrichment analysis
200 between control and combined stress conditions, as it displayed unique enrichment
201 patterns in both epigenetic marks and CS, and also exhibited the highest number of
202 differentially expressed proteins. Notably, 154 of these proteins were exclusively
203 differentially accumulated at this time point, showing biological relevance across various
204 functional processes.

205 Enrichment analysis of epigenetic marks identified H3K4me3 as the predominant
206 regulatory mark for differentially expressed proteins at 24 hours, prompting its
207 experimental validation. To this end, we performed a MNase-ChIP-qPCR at specific
208 target loci with four candidate stress-responsive genes: *NAT1*, *HEL12*, *ATP12*, and
209 *CPN60C*. These genes were chosen based on their known involvement in key cellular
210 processes relevant to stress response. *NAT1* is involved in protein acetylation, a critical
211 modification for regulating stress adaptation. *HEL12*, an RNA helicase, plays a role in
212 RNA processing and stability, both of which are essential under stress conditions. *ATP12*,
213 a mitochondrial ATP synthase subunit, is crucial for energy production, which is often
214 compromised during stress. Finally, *CPN60C*, a chaperonin, is involved in protein folding
215 and stabilization, which are particularly important when cells experience stress-induced
216 protein misfolding. These set of targets exhibited H3K4me3 enrichment in their promoter
217 regions and first exons based on *in silico* analyses. Further examination via genome
218 browser site-specific analysis revealed that these regions were also associated with
219 bivalent CS, while the remaining gene bodies displayed either active and/or repressive
220 CS.

221 MNase-ChIP-qPCR analysis (**Figure 2E**) confirmed the H3K4me3-mediated regulation
222 of *NAT1*, *HEL12*, *ATP12*, and *CPN60C* with distinctive patterns between conditions.
223 Control samples showed higher levels of this mark in *NAT1*, *HEL12*, and *ATP12*,
224 correlating with their elevated gene expression and protein accumulation under these
225 conditions. In contrast, *CPN60C* showed higher levels of H3K4me3 under combined
226 stress condition, consistent with its upregulation under stress.

227 Discussion

228 Epigenetic mechanisms play critical roles in acclimating stressful environments, with heir
229 inherent reversibility underscoring their adaptability (Cavalli and Heard, 2019). This
230 plasticity enables dynamic responses to environmental changes, where certain
231 epigenetic modifications may act as drivers of improved stress tolerance. In
232 *Chlamydomonas*, heat, drought and their combination trigger well-characterized, cellular
233 and metabolic pathways, revealing both adaptive responses and potential molecular
234 trade-offs (Colina et al., 2020a; Zhang et al., 2022; Álvarez et al., 2025). To further
235 explore the interplay between epigenetics and stress adaptation, we developed
236 ChlamytinaTool, an integrative resource that links the epigenome and proteome,
237 providing deeper insights into how cells coordinate stress responses. This tool provides
238 valuable insights into the regulatory mechanisms underlying climate change adaptation
239 in *Chlamydomonas*.

240 ChlamytinaTool addresses a key question in microalgae research: can my
241 proteins/transcripts be epigenetically regulated? The tool allows to perform enrichment
242 analysis for a broad range of epigenetic marks, including histone modifications
243 (H3K4me3, H3K27ac, H3K9me3, H3K27me3, H3K36me3), transcriptional regulators
244 (RNA polymerase II, transcription factor PSR1), DNA methylation (5mC, 6mA), and
245 nucleosome positioning. Additionally, we generate a 23-CS model, which integrates
246 these marks. Despite *Chlamydomonas* being a widely used model organism, epigenetic
247 analyses, especially those integrating chromatin state models, remain scarce. In
248 contrast, numerous epigenomic studies in other plant models have generated datasets
249 to investigate epigenetic regulation in processes such as stress responses and
250 developmental transitions (Hu et al., 2021; Ikeda et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2017; Schmid et
251 al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2017; Zhao et al., 2024). For well-established higher plant models
252 like *Arabidopsis thaliana*, *Oryza sativa*, and *Zea mays*, curated public databases have
253 been developed to infer chromatin states by integrating previously characterized
254 epigenetic marks, enabling the decoding of underlying regulatory mechanisms (Liu et al.,
255 2018; Roces et al., 2024). In *Chlamydomonas*, only one previous effort (Ngan et al.,
256 2015) defines chromatin states, and it was limited to a several number of histone
257 modifications without integrating other regulatory features. Our 23-CS model represents
258 a significant step forward, incorporating a broader range of epigenetic marks and
259 regulatory factors, and enabling a more comprehensive interpretation of epigenome-
260 proteome/transcriptome relationships. In addition to its core analytical capabilities,
261 ChlamytinaTool includes user-oriented features that streamline transcriptomic and
262 proteomic data analysis, reducing dependency on external software. The platform allows
263 for in-tool normalization, differential expression analysis, and targeted exploration of
264 genes or proteins of interest through an integrated genome browser. This combination
265 of epigenetic enrichment analysis, chromatin state modelling, and downstream functional
266 analysis in a single interface empowers researchers to conduct end-to-end
267 investigations, from raw data to biological interpretation, efficiently and intuitively.

268 The development of a 23-chromatin-state model for *Chlamydomonas* represents a
269 significant advancement in the epigenomic characterization of this model microalga.
270 While a 40-state model offered a better mathematical fit, its complexity limited its
271 interpretability. The selection of a 23-state configuration thus reflects a careful balance
272 between statistical robustness and biological insight, aligning with common practices in
273 other plant epigenomics studies, where interpretability has guided model selection (An
274 et al., 2024; Baker et al., 2015; Ernst and Kellis, 2017; Pérez et al., 2021). Functionally,
275 the classification of CS into five major categories, active, repressive, bivalent, low-signal,

276 and quiescent, captures the diversity and complexity of epigenetic regulation in
277 Chlamydomonas. Notably, the high proportion of bivalent states suggests dynamic
278 regulatory landscapes, where genes may be poised for activation or repression
279 depending on environmental or developmental cues. This feature is reminiscent of
280 findings in higher eukaryotes and may reflect conserved regulatory strategies (Roces et
281 al., 2024). The genome-wide annotation of chromatin states across diverse genomic
282 features further enhances the interpretability of the model. We provide a framework for
283 linking epigenetic landscapes to gene function and regulation. These annotations not
284 only support hypothesis-driven research but also enable data-driven discovery of
285 regulatory elements potentially involved in stress response or developmental transitions.
286 Overall, this chromatin state map provides an unprecedented resolution of the
287 Chlamydomonas' epigenome and fills a critical gap in algal functional genomics. It sets
288 the stage for comparative epigenomics with other plant models and supports broader
289 applications in systems biology and stress research.

290 Our *in silico* results showed that the most significant shift in Chlamydomonas' proteome
291 under combined heat and drought stress occurs 24 hours after stress application with
292 several exclusive differentially accumulated proteins related to protein biosynthesis,
293 energy metabolism, redox homeostasis, and other pathways linked to stress response.
294 At this point, H3K4me3 enrichment emerges as a key regulatory mechanism, suggesting
295 its role in driving protein accumulation changes during stress response. This aligns with
296 prior findings where H3K4me3 acts as a driver modification in Chlamydomonas' diurnal
297 cycle (Strenkert et al., 2022). Furthermore, increased RNA polymerase II enrichment
298 indicates heightened transcriptional activity at 24 hours. Notably, our CS analysis
299 demonstrates a time-dependent progression of chromatin accessibility during stress
300 exposure. The 24-hour timepoint appears particularly significant, marked by the
301 emergence of specific active and bivalent chromatin states that facilitate this stress
302 adaptation transition. This epigenetic reprogramming suggests a coordinated temporal
303 mechanism for stress response in Chlamydomonas.

304 An experimental protocol was applied to determine PTM enrichments at specific target
305 loci, serving to validate both the *in silico* predictions and the overall output of
306 ChlamytinaTool. To test whether the potential epigenetic regulation by H3K4me3 could
307 influence differential protein accumulation at 24 hours of stress, we applied MNase-ChIP-
308 qPCR protocol and conducted targeted experiments that support this association. The
309 validation of specific epigenetic targets using MNase-ChIP-like protocols coupled to
310 qPCR is a widely employed approach to confirm *in silico* predictions at the locus level

311 (Kim and Dekker, 2018; Song et al., 2021). *NAT1*, *HEL12*, *ATP12*, and *CPN60C* were
312 selected as potential stress marker genes based on *in silico* analysis, as their encoded
313 proteins showed exclusive differential accumulation at 24 hours of stress. These four
314 candidate stress markers showed a potential presence of active mark H3K4me3 in two
315 different genomic regions: promoter and first exons. These findings suggest that
316 H3K4me3 mediated regulation primarily targets promoters and first exons in these
317 genes. The identical H3K4me3 enrichment patterns observed in both the promoter and
318 first exons suggest a greater potential for epigenetic regulation within bivalent CS. As
319 both promoter and first exons are proximal to the transcription start site, they often share
320 similar epigenetic regulation, which differs from that of the downstream gene body.
321 Previous studies report similar findings, where 5mC-mediated hypermethylation in
322 promoters and first exons is associated with repression, while gene body methylation is
323 linked to active expression (Anastasiadi et al., 2018). These regions were associated
324 with bivalent CS, while the remainder of the gene body displayed either active or
325 repressive CS exclusively. These regions, that characterize the simultaneous presence
326 of activating and repressive marks, may undergo more dynamic transitions between
327 heterochromatin and euchromatin states.

328 MNase-ChIP-qPCR and RT-qPCR analyses revealed a consistent correlation between
329 H3K4me3 enrichment patterns and stress-induced expression changes, providing
330 compelling evidence for H3K4me3's role as a key epigenetic regulator of the 24-hour
331 stress response in *Chlamydomonas*. Biologically, these genes are associated with key
332 cellular processes potentially involved in stress responses. *NAT1* encodes N-TERMINAL
333 ACETYLTRANSFERASE implicated in protein modification and stability. A previous
334 study reports that NAT-depleted plants show increased drought tolerance (Linster and
335 Wirtz, 2018). These findings are consistent with the lower protein abundance and
336 reduced gene expression we observed under combined heat and drought stress. *HEL12*
337 encodes a DEAD-BOX ATP-DEPENDENT RNA HELICASE that participates in RNA
338 processing catalysing the unwind of double-stranded RNAs. A systemic-wide study in
339 *Chlamydomonas* reveals an up-regulation of RNA helicases under cold stress (Valledor
340 et al., 2013). Since RNA unwinding reaction can occur spontaneously at high
341 temperatures, the need for helicase activity decreases under heat stress. This may
342 explain the downregulation of *HEL12* gene expression and protein abundance observed
343 under combined heat and drought conditions; *ATP12* encodes MITOCHONDRIAL F1F0
344 ATP SYNTHASE BETA SUBUNIT, which couples the proton gradient across the inner
345 mitochondrial membrane to ATP synthesis, linking energy homeostasis to stress
346 conditions. Oxidative stress negatively impacts ATP synthase, with evidence showing

347 degradation linked to the activation of proteases. Among other subunits, beta is the most
348 sensitive to different oxidative agents. However, degradation of beta subunit still
349 maintains a residual activity of ATP synthase, able to sustain metabolism response
350 during stress (Zancani et al., 2020). Our findings of reduced gene expression and protein
351 abundance for ATP12 under combined heat and drought stress align with previous
352 reports linking reactive oxygen species production to ATP synthase damage (Li et al.,
353 2014). In contrast to the above candidates, *CPN60C*, which encodes CHAPERONIN
354 60C, shows higher protein abundance under combined heat and drought stress. This
355 protein supports chloroplast protein folding under stress and shows an accumulation
356 during heat acclimation (Ries et al., 2023). These findings are consistent with our
357 observations of elevated *CPN60C* gene expression and protein levels under stress
358 conditions. The unique stress-responsive behaviour of these genes at 24 hours makes
359 them strong candidates for investigating time-specific epigenetic regulation during
360 acclimation.

361 Overall, ChlamytinaTool offers a comprehensive and optimized approach for
362 investigating epigenetic regulation in *Chlamydomonas*. By integrating CS models,
363 epigenetic marks enrichment analysis, and downstream transcript and protein
364 processing data, the tool provides valuable insights into how this microalga responds to
365 environmental challenges. The experimental validation of H3K4me3 as a key regulatory
366 mark further emphasizes its role in stress adaptation, highlighting the broader potential
367 of epigenetic modifications in facilitating response to climate change in microalgae.

368 Material and methods

369 Development of ChlamytinaTool

370 Data collection

371 We collected epigenomic data (**Table S2**) from model species *Chlamydomonas*
372 *reinhardtii* published in recent years: chromatin immunoprecipitation (ChIP-seq), whole
373 genome bisulfite (WGBS), methylated DNA precipitation (MeDIP-seq), and micrococcal
374 nuclease digestion (MNase-seq). ChIP-seq data including histone post-translational
375 modifications (PTMs) H3K4me3, H3K4me2, H3K27ac, H3K9me3, H3K27me3,
376 H3K36me3, RNA polymerase II, and transcription factor PHOSPHORUS STRESS
377 RESPONSE 1 (PSR1) are available in NCBI under accession PRJNA255778 (Ngan et
378 al., 2015). WGBS data considering 5-methylcytosine DNA methylation (5mC) are
379 available under accession PRJNA285349 (Lopez et al., 2015). 6-methyladenosine DNA

380 methylation (6mA) by MeDIP-seq, and nucleosome positioning data by MNase-seq are
381 available under accession PRJNA264813 (Fu et al., 2015).

382 **Epigenomic data processing**

383 ChIP-seq raw reads were not re-processed, we directly collected public BED files
384 generated in Ngan *et al.*, (2015). 5mC, 6mA and MNase-seq raw reads were processed
385 for generating BED files containing methylation peaks and nucleosome positioning,
386 respectively (**Figure 1A**). Raw reads were trimmed and adapters were removed using
387 trim_galore v0.6.6 as an interface to CutAdapt (Martin, 2011). Duplicated sequences
388 were removed using FilterReads.py, a module of BS-Seeker2 v2.1.8 (Guo et al., 2013).
389 The remaining reads were aligned to Phytozome-*Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* CC-503
390 v5.6 genome indexed (and converted to bisulfite with Bismark v0.21.0 (Krueger and
391 Andrews, 2011) for WGBS data) using bowtie2 algorithm v2.3.4.1 (Langmead and
392 Salzberg, 2012). Aligned reads were sorted with SAMtools v1.9. Peak calling signal track
393 building was performed with methylKit v1.10.0 (Akalin et al., 2012) for 5mC-WGBS and
394 with MACS v2.1.2 (Zhang et al., 2008) considering FDR < 0.1 for 6mA-MeDIP-seq.
395 Nucleosome positioning was performed employing DANPOS2 (Chen et al., 2013).

396 **Chromatin states definition and annotation**

397 We applied ChromHMM (Ernst and Kellis, 2017) to jointly infer *Chlamydomonas*
398 chromatin states (CS) using diverse chromatin modifications BED tracks as input (**Figure**
399 **1A**). Tracks were binarized in 150 bp bins, since we had nucleosome positioning files
400 that allowed us to establish an optimum of 150 bp for specific case of *Chlamydomonas*.
401 For binarization, we used *-center* argument that consider the center of the peaks to
402 assign the presence of a mark. To further improve interpretability of the states,
403 annotations and descriptions were performed. We annotated CS by overlaps and by
404 neighbourhoods. Annotation by overlaps was based on overlapping with gene elements
405 while annotation by neighbourhoods was based on distance to different gene elements.
406 Additionally, we included CpG islands annotation formatting DNA sequence (Stothard,
407 2000).

408 **ChlamytinaTool extra-utilities**

409 Chromatin states and epigenomic marks were integrated with LOLA package (Sheffield
410 and Bock, 2016) to perform enrichment analysis of proteins/transcripts based on
411 genomic regions overlaps (**Figure 1A**). Analysis requires three components: (1) input
412 (query set as genomic regions on BED format); (2) background, the choice depends on
413 the biological question; and (3) region data base sets that are to be tested for overlap

414 with inputs (available CS and the different epigenetic marks included in the tool).
415 ChlamytinaTool also includes extra functions to complete protein/transcript downstream
416 analysis (**Figure 1A**). We generated a data prepare script that performs differential
417 expression analysis employing *limma* (Ritchie et al., 2015), unwanted variation
418 correction with *sva* (Leek et al., 2024), Phytozome accession liftover, intersection
419 between proteins/transcripts of different treatments using *nVennR* (Pérez-Silva et al.,
420 2018), and BED data generation (possible backgrounds and inputs for *LOLA*
421 enrichments). Additionally, a JBrowse epigenome browser (Buels et al., 2016) was
422 conducted focusing on a site-specific approach (**Figure 1A**).

423 **Tool availability**

424 We developed Chlamy(Chlamydomonas)tina(chromatin)Tool to provide public
425 availability of the CS generated in this work and to facilitate future research aiming to link
426 transcript expression or protein abundance in *Chlamydomonas* under different
427 experimental conditions with epigenetic patterns.

428 ChlamytinaTool is available via GitHub at <https://github.com/RocesV/Chlamytina> and via
429 docker at <https://hub.docker.com/rocesv/chlamytina>.

430 Epi-proteomics landscape under combined heat and drought stress

431 **Data and plant acquisition**

432 Plant material and proteomic dataset used for the integrative analysis and the
433 experimental validation were obtained from Álvarez *et al.* (2025). Briefly, the proteome
434 of *Chlamydomonas* under control and combined heat and drought stress (38 °C and 15%
435 w/v polyethylene glycol (PEG) 8000) conditions in four sampling points (0, 5, 24, 72, and
436 120 h) has been re-analysed and integrated considering the utilities included in
437 ChlamytinaTool. Proteomic raw data was processed with Proteome Discoverer 3.0
438 (Thermo Scientific, Bremen, Germany) considering filters and pre-processing workflow
439 followed on Álvarez *et al.* (2025) (**Table S1**). For this proteomic re-analysis, abundances
440 were normalized by sample centric approach and multiplied by average intensity of all
441 samples and transformed employing a $\log_{10}(x+1)$ transformation.

442 **In silico analysis of epigenetic modifications**

443 ChlamytinaTool was employed to explore the potential epigenetic regulation within the
444 proteomic dataset. Protein abundances were normalized (*normalizeQuantiles*), followed
445 by differential expression analysis (*limma*), and intersection analysis (*nVennR*) of
446 proteins across different treatments. Comparisons between control and stress samples

447 at each time were considered of all possible two-by-two comparisons performed in the
448 differential expression analysis (**Table S1**). Resulting BED data were used as query sets
449 for enrichment analysis based on genomic regions overlap, using *LOLA* package, and
450 generating heatmaps. Two different backgrounds were considered: whole proteome
451 (universe background) and set of differentially expressed proteins (differential
452 background) (**Table S1**). Different epigenetic marks and CS from ChlamytinaTool were
453 considered as region data base sets and tested for overlap with inputs.

454 **Experimental validation of H3K4me3 dynamics**

455 An MNase-ChIP-qPCR protocol was used with three biological samples generated in the
456 combined heat and drought stress experiment. ChIP was performed as described by
457 Strenkert *et al.*, (2011) and coupled with a previous MNase digestion based on Mozgová
458 *et al.*, (2015), with several modifications, including the reduction of cross-linking time to
459 5 min. MNase digestion (Micrococcal Nuclease, New England BioLabs, Cat No M0247S)
460 was performed with to 10 units per 100 μ L with a 16-minute incubation for an initial cell
461 density of $5 \cdot 10^5$ cell/mL. PTM evaluated was active mark H3K4me3 and antibodies
462 specific for the following epitopes were used: H3 (Abcam, ab1791) and H3K4me3
463 (Diagenode, Cat No C15410003-10).

464 *In silico* analysis was used for the selection of the epigenetic mark for the study and the
465 selection of gene stress markers. Experimental time point considered was 24 hours.
466 Potential gene stress markers were selected by filtering differentially abundance proteins
467 after 24 hours of combined heat and drought stress. Only differential proteins exclusives
468 at 24 hours were considered and non-annotated proteins were filtered out (**Table S1**).
469 Furthermore, genome browser integrated in ChlamytinaTool was used to identified
470 potential genomic regions with H3K4me3 positioning. Enrichment was evaluated in
471 promoter, defined as 2 kb upstream of the transcription start site (TSS) as well as in one
472 of the first two exons of the gene body. Subsequently, four candidates were selected
473 based on statistical significance (p-value) and the logarithm of fold change: *NAT1*,
474 *HEL12*, *ATP12*, and *CPN60C*.

475 To evaluate gene expression of selected stress markers (primers in **Table S3**), total RNA
476 was extracted following the procedure described in Valledor *et al.*, (2014). RNA
477 concentration was determined by a Nabi UV/Vis Nano Spectrophotometer (MicroDigital
478 Co.) and integrity was checked by agarose gel electrophoresis. Next, cDNA was
479 synthesised by RevertAid kit (Thermo Scientific) using random hexamers and following
480 manufacturer's instructions. Targeted transcriptomics by qPCR analysis were carried out
481 by a CFX Connect™ Real-Time System (Bio-Rad) using SsoAdvanced Universal SYBR

482 Green Supermix (Bio-Rad) and results were evaluated using cycle threshold
483 comparative method (Ct). Three biological replicates and two analytical replicates per
484 treatment were considered. *RECEPTOR OF ACTIVATED PROTEIN KINASE C (RACK1)*
485 and *GLYCERALDEHYDE-3-PHOSPHATE DEHYDROGENASE A (GAP3)* were used as
486 reference genes for transcript level normalization (primers in **Table S3**).

487 qPCR analysis was performed to evaluate MNase-ChIP results in the four selected
488 stress markers (primers in **Table S3**) employing same Real-Time system and
489 polymerase. Three biological replicates and two analytical replicates per treatment were
490 considered. Enrichments in H3K4me3 were evaluated considering a normalization by
491 the input fraction and a background correction. Results were presented as a relative
492 enrichment of H3K4me3 compared to H3, calculated as: $\text{input fraction (\%)} = 100 \cdot 2^{-\text{Ct}_{(\text{Input})} - \text{Ct}_{(\text{IP})}}$, where IP includes H3, H3K4me3 and NoAb samples. Signal was corrected
493 using NoAb sample as background: $\text{corrected signal (\%)} = \text{input fraction}_{\text{IP}} (\%) - \text{input}$
494 $\text{fraction}_{\text{NoAb}} (\%)$. Finally, the formula: $\text{corrected signal}_{\text{H3K4me3}} (\%) / \text{corrected signal}_{\text{H3}} (\%)$
495 was used to evaluate H3K4me3 enrichment.

497 Statistical evaluation was carried out in R 4.2. (R Core Team, 2021) under RStudio IDE
498 (RStudio Team, 2020) with bundled core packages in addition to those specific to the
499 *rstatix*, *emmeans*, *agricolae*, *ggpubr*, and *ggplot2* packages. The normality of the data
500 (Shapiro-Wilk test) was checked in addition to their homoscedasticity (Levene test).
501 Comparisons were made between different treatments using one-way ANOVA test
502 followed by Tukey's post-hoc test (parametric variables). In all cases, confidence level
503 was established at 95% (p-value ≤ 0.05).

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509 Author's Contributions

510 A.A, V.R, M.M. and L.V. conceived the study. A.A., I.M., M.F., M.M. and L.V. designed the
511 research. A.A. and R.K. performed the experimental validation. A.A. collected datasets,
512 performed the *in silico* analysis, draw the figures, and wrote the manuscript under

513 supervision of M.M. and L.V. ChlamytinaTool and its utilities were developed by V.R. All
514 authors revised, read, and approved the final manuscript.

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763 Figure legends

764 **Figure 1. (A)** Overview of bioinformatics workflow followed for ChlamytinaTool
765 implementation. **(B)** Distribution of epigenetic marks included in ChlamytinaTool. **(C)** CS
766 model generated. State emissions of epigenetic marks and genomic annotations based
767 on different genomic regions.

768 **Figure 2. (A)** Number of differential proteins between control and combined heat and
769 drought stress at different experimental points. **(B)** MapMan annotation of regulated
770 exclusive proteins at 24h. **(C)** Enrichment of *Chlamydomonas*' proteome under combined
771 heat and drought stress in different epigenetic marks and **(D)** in the 23 chromatin states
772 generated. Universe refers to using the whole proteome as background, while differential
773 refers to using only the differentially expressed proteins as background. **(E)** Expression
774 of *NAT1*, *HEL12*, *ATP12*, and *CPN60C* under control and combined heat and drought
775 stress determined by RT-qPCR. Evaluation of H3K4me3 enrichments in promoter and
776 first exons of these genes determined by MNase-ChIP-qPCR.

777 **Supplemental Information**

778 **Table S1.** Differential proteins and backgrounds.

779 **Table S2.** List of sequencing files collected in ChlamytinaTool.

780 **Table S3.** Selection and evaluation of candidates